

Evolutionary chemistry of carbon as a molecular basis for ecoadaptive technologies

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Organic matter on Earth is involved in continuous processes of de novo synthesis and decay, which at the global level correspond to photosynthesis and humification comprising the global ecosystem metabolism. Humic systems play the role of ecosystem metabolome and bear the molecular imprint of climatic, geological and geographical conditions as well as the influence of anthropogenic activity. The study and systematization of the molecular composition of humic systems is an essential prerequisite for ecosystem metabolomics aimed at molecular diagnostics of global processes of organic matter transformation. The optimal way to solve this problem is to use Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry (FTICR MS), which has an extremely high resolution and distinguishes millions of carbon atoms with different chemical environments in humic systems. We report here about the developed a highly efficient algorithm for analyzing information-rich mass spectra for humic systems - total mass difference algorithm (TMDS), which formed the basis of many software.

An important problem of geoecology is the restoration of life support functions of polluted and disturbed ecosystems as a result of anthropogenic impact. Humic systems play a key role in self-purification, self-organization and self-healing of contaminated ecosystems. Therefore, a very urgent problem is the reproduction of these natural mechanisms in chemicals, materials and processes for development of ecoadaptive technologies for remediation of disturbed environments. The prospects of this area are confirmed by the results of our many years of research. Few examples will be given in this report. For the first time, it is proposed to use solid stabilizers to create a new generation of dispersants and washing agents based on Pickering emulsions for cleaning oil-contaminated media. This approach was used for in situ technology for cleaning soils from diesel fuel pollution using humic-bentonite compounds, designed to clean contaminated soils in the Norilsk area. The knowledge gained can be used for solving other geological problems. Currently we imply accelerated in situ humification for remediation of sludge lignin dumpsite at the Baykal lake located at the former Baykal Paper Mill facilities. The aim of our efforts is to achieve dewatering and oxidative polymerization of lignin which will provide mechanically stable and fertile grounds for plants.

Thus implication of molecular chemistry of humic systems evolution may contribute to solving organic waste problem which is one of the main task for the circle economy and contribute for targeted application of ecoadaptive technologies.

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